

GENOMED4ALL USE CASE META DATA AVAILABLE FOR OPEN SCIENCE

The GenoMed4ALL project

Accumulating evidence points towards personalised medicine to treat and manage common, rare and ultra-rare haematological diseases. Advanced statistics and machine learning approaches may contribute to the exploitation of omics and clinical data in patient-oriented research and decision-making. [GenoMed4ALL is an European project](#), funded under the call “Societal Challenges - Health, demographic change and well-being” with grant agreement ID: 101017549, with start date 1 January 2021 and end date 30 June 2025.

GenoMed4ALL aims to demonstrate the potential and benefits of trustable and explainable AI technologies to exploit the powerful set of “omics” data for advancing research and personalized medicine. The use cases are three Haematological Diseases (HDs), oncological and non-oncological. HDs involve a class of up to 450 disorders in six large groups. The overall number of patients affected with haematological malignancies account about 5% of cancers. Most HDs can cause chronic health problems and many of them are life-threatening conditions requiring numerous resources and multidisciplinary teams, thus representing a public health challenge.

The use cases:

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS)

Multiple Myeloma (MM)

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS)

The Disease

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS) are a group of bone marrow failure disorders that typically affect the elderly. Patients suffer from blood cytopenia (low blood cell counts), since their bone marrow is no longer able to produce enough healthy blood cells. The disease is also known as a form of blood cancer, and in some patients can evolve into acute myeloid leukaemia (AML), which is usually fatal if not treated.

Clinical Aims

Prevention based on Genomic Screening	Investigate factors that influence the development of MDS, enabling early-stage identification of individuals at risk.
Omics-based Classification and Prognosis	Personalized predictive models through integration of comprehensive genomic and clinical information.
Omics-based Clinical Decision	Making AI-based algorithms to stratify the individual probability of response to specific treatments.

Study design: Multi-centric retrospective, observational, non-interventional study

Specific objectives

- To understand better MDS biology
- To enhance prognostic/predictive capacity of currently available tools
- To apply treatments in a more targeted way

Study Population ¹

An international retrospective cohort of 2,043 patients affected with primary MDS according to 2016 WHO criteria

Genomic Screening

- At diagnosis, cytogenetic analysis was performed using standard G-banding and karyotypes were classified using the International System for Cytogenetic Nomenclature Criteria.
- Mutation screening of 47 genes related to myeloid neoplasms was performed on DNA from peripheral blood granulocytes or bone marrow mononuclear cells

Clinical Partners

1. ICH (Humanitas Mirasole)
2. IBSAL (Institute of Biomedical Research of Salamanca)
3. APHP (Assistance Publique – Hôpitaux de Paris)
4. MLL (Münchener Leukämielabor GmbH)
5. UL (Universität Leipzig)

About the data

Study of MDS has been rapidly transformed by genome characterization and there is increasing evidence that mutation screening may add significant information to currently available prognostic scores.

Somatic mutations occur in the genomes of hematopoietic stem cells at a low, but detectable frequency during normal DNA replication. Any genetic alteration that causes a selective advantage relative to other self-renewing cells will lead to clonal dominance

¹ Bersanelli et al, "Classification and Personalized Prognostic Assessment on the Basis of Clinical and Genomic Features in Myelodysplastic Syndromes", Journal of Clinical Oncology, Volume 39, Issue 11, 2021

(clonal haematopoiesis, CH). The consequence of CH is genomic instability leading to increased risk of acquiring additional mutations and to develop MDS, solid cancer and other illnesses. MDS datasets provide comprehensive genomic and transcriptomic information essential for understanding clonal haematopoiesis and MDS. It includes targeted mutation screening of 47 genes associated with clonal haematopoiesis, offering valuable insights into early genetic alterations that may predispose individuals to haematological malignancies. Additionally, targeted mutation screening in MDS patients, along with RNA sequencing of hematopoietic progenitors, enables the study of molecular mechanisms driving disease progression and therapeutic resistance.

Whole-exome and whole-genome sequencing data further facilitate the identification of novel pathogenic variants and potential biomarkers. Moreover, targeted mutation screening in MDS patients who underwent transplantation provides critical data for understanding genetic factors influencing post-transplant outcomes.

Clinical data collected: Complete blood count - Bone marrow blasts percentage at diagnosis - Cytogenetic abnormalities - Presence of transfusion dependency - Comorbidities - Type of treatment - Disease evolution (if applicable) - Overall survival.

Metadata

In the file Genomed4All_MDS_Metadata.xls metadata from MDS use case are reported, as the following excerpt

→ CLINICAL DATA

CLINICAL DATA	VARIANT TYPE	VARIANT ANNOTATION
ID	string	Unique patient ID
Sex	string	F = female; M = male
Age	numeric	Age at diagnosis, years
WHO 2016 MDS Classification	string	Classification according to the 2016 WHO Classification of MDS (https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2016-03-643544)
Leukocytes x10 ⁶ /uL	numeric	Leukocytes x10 ⁶ /uL at diagnosis
Neutrophils x10 ⁶ /uL	numeric	Neutrophils x10 ⁶ /uL at diagnosis
Monocytes x10 ⁶ /uL	numeric	Monocytes x10 ⁶ /uL at diagnosis
Hemoglobin g/L	numeric	Hemoglobin g/L at diagnosis
Platelets x10 ⁶ /uL	numeric	Platelets x10 ⁶ /uL at diagnosis
% bone marrow blasts	numeric	% bone marrow blasts at diagnosis
% bone marrow ring sideroblasts	numeric	% bone marrow ring sideroblasts at diagnosis

Excerpt from MDS Clinical Data Metadata

Aggregated Data

The characteristics of the cohort to which the metadata refer has been fully described in the following paper: Bersanelli M et al. Classification and Personalized Prognostic Assessment on the Basis of Clinical and Genomic Features in Myelodysplastic Syndromes. J Clin Oncol. 2021 Apr 10;39(11):1223-1233

[10.1200/JCO.20.01659](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.20.01659)